

Title:

Fabrication of periodically micro-patterned magnetite nanoparticles by laser interference controlled electrodeposition

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Abstract

This paper introduces a laser interference controlled electrochemical deposition (LIED) method for direct fabrication of periodically micro-patterned magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles (NPs). In this work, Fe_3O_4 NPs were controllably synthesized on the areas where the photoconductive electrode was exposed to the periodically patterned interferometric laser irradiation during the electrodeposition. Thus, the micro-pattern of Fe_3O_4 NPs was controlled by interferometric laser pattern and the crystallization of the particles was controlled by laser interference intensity and electrochemical deposition conditions. The bottom-up electrochemical approach was combined with a top down laser interference methodology. This maskless method allows for in situ fabrication of periodically patterned magnetite NPs on the micro-scale by electrodeposition under room temperature and atmospheric pressure conditions. In the experiment, Fe_3O_4 NPs with the mean grain size below 100 nm in the pattern of 5 μm line array were achieved within the deposition time of 100 seconds. The experiment results have shown that the proposed method is a one-step approach in fabricating large areas of periodically micro-patterned magnetite NPs.

Key words: magnetite nanoparticles; laser interference pattern; micro-patterned; grain size distribution; electrodeposition.

1. Introduction

Micro and nano-patterned magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) are widely investigated recently due to the increasing demand of nano-electronic devices, sensors [1,2], systems for sorting and manipulating cells [3], and high-density data storage devices [4]. Nanoparticle-based structures specifically concern two-dimensional ordered arrays of

MNPs on solid substrates which possess different properties of magnetic anisotropy [5,6]. Such structures are particularly promising for the manufacturing of high-capacity bit-patterned media (BPM) [7], which can potentially extend the storage capacities of magnetic hard disk drives (HDDs) and replace present magnetic films. Conventional synthesis of patterned thin-films of MNPs requires a high temperature of hundreds of degrees Celsius and high vacuum sputtering process with specialized equipment [8,9]. Therefore, the development of economical synthesis methods for the fabrication of MNPs with a controllable pattern, period and crystallisation is required [10].

Currently, Iron oxides such as magnetite (Fe_3O_4) can be obtained by cathodic or anodic electrochemical synthesis methods [11-14]. Martinez et al. reported that iron oxide-oxyhydroxide layers in different phases were able to be produced by the control of applied voltages and electrolyte compositions [11]. Meng et al. reported the fabrication of hematite ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) nanoparticles (NPs) on ITO films by electrodeposition [12]. The electrochemical deposition of Fe_3O_4 micro-nano particles on carbon nanofiber buckypapers was reported [13]. Cathodic electrodeposition of Fe_3O_4 thin films by galvanostatic deposition at elevated temperatures was also reported [14]. It can be seen from the reported approaches that the NPs are fabricated with unpatterned electrodes in the electrochemical deposition processes. Therefore, patterned distributions of particles cannot be obtained by the reported methods, and there is the need to develop methods for direct fabrication of patterned particles.

Normally, lithography-assisted assembly is the main methodology for organizing MNPs into micro/nano structured patterns on a substrate. Stamp-assisted structuration method is most widely used for patterning MNPs on surfaces by micro-contact printing (μCP). A

self-assembled monolayer (SAM) was fabricated as a template, then the MNPs were attached to the structured surfaces [15-18]. Also, Cavallini et al. reported the method of microinjection molding in capillaries to pattern Fe₃O₄ NPs in micrometric stripes and dots on mica [19]. Electron beam lithography (EBL) and photolithography are mostly used in the lithography-assisted structuration method to fabricate physical templates that can be used to structure the MNPs. The topographically structured surfaces physically guide the assembly of MNPs to specific areas [20-22]. Recently, biomimetic templates are used for the synthesis and assembly of MNPs. Patterning of magnetite NPs onto gold substrates by biomineralization and biotemplate has been previously reported [23-26]. Although different methods for the fabrication of ordered MNPs have been developed, the patterned templates obtained by relatively complex traditional lithography steps are usually required. The optically induced electrochemical deposition (OED) method [27-29], previously developed by Li et al., used programmable light patterns to produce controlled and localized electric fields in a photosensitive microfluidic chip, for fabricating metal thin films in nano-devices.

In this study, we combined the electrodeposition with the OED method, and presented a laser interference controlled electrochemical deposition (LIED) method to achieve direct and high efficient fabrication of periodically micro-patterned Fe₃O₄ NPs on large areas. Laser interference irradiation was used in the LIED process to generate periodic microstructures over large areas with high fidelity and minimal substrate treatments [30-33]. Fe₃O₄ NPs in a periodical pattern of 5 μm line arrays were directly fabricated by LIED over an area of 1 cm² within 100 second deposition time, and the mean grain size of the NPs was below 100 nm. The process was performed in one-step at room temperature

and atmospheric pressure conditions, while requiring no templates and complex techniques.

The LIED method has good controllability for the fabrication of patterned MNPs. During electrodeposition, the synthesis of MNPs occurs selectively on the areas where the photoconductive cathode is exposed to the interferometric laser irradiation in the electrolyte. Therefore, the micro-pattern period along with the pattern of the MNPs is controlled by the interferometric laser pattern. The nucleation and growth of Fe₃O₄ NPs are controlled by the laser interference intensity and electrochemical deposition conditions of the applied potential and deposition time.

Periodically micro-patterned Fe₃O₄ NPs fabricated by LIED method on hydrogenated amorphous silicon (α -Si:H) were investigated for the first time to understand the patterning mechanism of the laser interference controlled process and the electrodeposition reaction. Also, the effects of interference intensity, electrodeposition potential and time on the grain size, crystallization and morphology of Fe₃O₄ were subsequently studied. The optimization of conditions in electrosynthesis was also carried out.

2. Methods

2.1. Experiment

A. Preparation of electrolyte. The electrolyte used in each experiment was a mixture of 4 mM ferrous chlorides (FeCl₂•4H₂O, Xilong Chemical) and 8 mM ferric chlorides (FeCl₃•6H₂O, Tianjin Kaitong Chemical Reagent) containing Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ ions with a molar ratio of 1:2, based on the co-precipitation method for the preparation of bare Fe₃O₄ NPs [34]. The electrolyte was put in a 150 mL rectangular quartz beaker. All electrolytes were

prepared from analytical grade reagents without further purification, and deionized water was from the Millipore water purification system. The electrolyte was kept at room temperature during the entire electrodeposition process.

B. Electrode Fabrication. The photoconductive electrode consists of an ITO glass substrate (square resistance is 8Ω) with an α -Si:H layer deposited on the substrate surface by a plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) process. During the PECVD, one part of the ITO glass was covered with a mask, leaving a non-deposited area used as a bottom conductive electrode. Then, a copper conductive tape was connected to the exposed bottom ITO electrode so as to enhance the conductivity when applying a DC current to the electrode, as shown in the enlarged image of Fig. 1(a). Specifically, the thickness of the α -Si:H layer was 100 nm. The counter electrode was an iron plate and the reference electrode was a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Prior to the electrodeposition, the three-electrode setup was immersed in the electrolyte, and the photoconductive electrode was placed on the outermost side. The uncoated side was directed toward the beaker wall with the α -Si:H film oriented toward the inside of the beaker. The immersion depth of the electrodes was consistent to ensure that the area deposited in each experiment was about 1 cm^2 , and the position of the electrodes was fixed.

C. Experiment Setup. The laser interference irradiation process was carried out by exposing the photoconductive electrode surface to a continuous wave Nd: YAG laser (CNI MSL-457, $\lambda = 457 \text{ nm}$, maximum power = 100 mW) in a two-beam interference system. The laser power was measured with the Laser Power and Energy Meter (Thorlabs PM200). The schematic diagram of the interference system setup is shown in Fig. 1(a). W is the half-wave plate, and P is the polarization prism. M is the mirror, and BS is the beam splitter.

In the experiment, the two incident beams followed a symmetrical configuration with the azimuthal angles of $\varphi_1 = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi_2 = 180^\circ$ and the same incident angle of 2.6° . The polarization mode of TE-TE was employed. It was assumed that the initial phases were zero and the amplitudes of the two beams were identical. The interference system was mounted on the outside of the beaker to ensure the homogeneous illumination during deposition. The laser beams were expanded so that they illuminated an area of 1 cm^2 . The beams were reflected off the mirrors and passed through the beaker, electrolyte and ITO substrate. Then they were intersected and interfered on the back of the α -Si:H film. An electrochemical workstation (Model CHI660D, Shanghai Chenhua) was interfaced to a personal computer for collecting data. The measurement method of chronopotentiometry (CP) was used for the electrochemical deposition. The cathode of the electrochemical workstation was connected to the ITO layer of the photoconductive substrate via the conductive copper tape. The complete LIED system is shown in Fig. 1(a).

D. Fabrication of Fe_3O_4 NPs by LIED method. When a DC current was applied between the cathode and the metallic anode, concurrently, laser interference irradiated on the photoconductive substrate, and the electrochemical deposition was carried out with the different time periods from 0 to 800 s. Finally, the deposited NPs were rinsed with DI water and dried with nitrogen. A large area of Fe_3O_4 NPs in the pattern of $5 \mu\text{m}$ line arrays was obtained on the α -Si:H surface as shown in Fig. 1(b). The grain size distribution of particles has a good agreement with the distribution of the interferometric laser intensity, as shown in Fig. 1(c). The details will be discussed in Section 4.2.

2.2 Characterization

A scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to examine the morphologies and

grain distributions. All deposited samples were imaged by a high-resolution SEM (FEI QUANT-250 FEG, at the 5 kV accelerated voltage). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to identify the element constituents of the deposits. The crystal phase of samples was characterized by XPS (ESCALAB 250).

Fig. 2 shows the XPS spectra of the Fe₃O₄ NPs fabricated on the α -Si:H surface with the current density of 1.0 mA cm⁻², deposition time of 100 seconds and irradiated interferometric laser power density of 1.5 mW cm⁻². The peaks of the C 1s, O 2p, Fe 3p and Fe 2p are included in the NPs, as shown in Fig. 2(a). Fe₃O₄ is alternatively expressed as FeO·Fe₂O₃. From the spectra in Fig. 2(b), the double peak positions of Fe 2p_{3/2} and Fe 2p_{1/2} are 710.88 and 724.48 eV, respectively, which are in agreement with the standard peak positions of Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ in the stoichiometric Fe₃O₄ [11,35]. The double peaks are broadened, corresponding to the contributions of Fe²⁺ (2p_{3/2}) and Fe²⁺ (2p_{1/2}) peaks. This situation confirms that the NPs are Fe₃O₄ rather than γ -Fe₂O₃ [36,37].

3 Patterning mechanism by LIED

The laser interference irradiation on the photoconductive cathode and an applied DC current concurrently perform the LIED patterning process. The photoconductivity of the irradiated α -Si:H can increase from 10⁻¹⁰ S m⁻¹ to approximately 10⁻³ S m⁻¹, resulting from the photoexcitation of electron-hole pairs. When the interferometric laser intensity reaches to a certain threshold, the incident interferometric laser pattern on the photoconductive substrate generates localized micro-patterns of high conductivity, leading to the creation of a patterned virtual photo-cathode or virtual electrode (VE). In this way, the patterned laser irradiation controls the electrodeposition reaction as an optical switch. As shown in Fig. 3(a), the interferometric laser pattern irradiated onto the α -Si:H substrate

of the cathode forms a patterned VE and guides the electron transfer with the pattern. Under an applied galvanostatic condition, a higher electrical potential could be dropped on the VE/electrolyte area than the non-irradiated interface. Due to the effects of electrophoretic force and Brownian motion, the mass transfers of ferrous irons and ferric irons are from the electrolyte solution to the reaction zone.

Then the adsorbed ferrous irons, ferric irons and hydroxyl ions generated from the reaction in Eq. (1), allow for the electrochemical synthesis of Fe₃O₄ in the electric double layer (EDL) [38,39] close to the VE, as shown in Eq. (2). At the VE, the evolution of hydrogen gas is accompanied by the formation of OH⁻ ions, which will lead to an increase of the local pH at the electrode surface.

The cathode reactions in the reaction zone can be expressed as

In the LIED system, the EDL at the interface between the VE and the electrolyte, plays a pivotal role for the overall reaction, because it provides the voltage potential and environment for the final product [40,41]. Fig. 3(b) shows a simplified equivalent circuit model of the LIED system, where C_a and R_a denote the capacitance and resistance of the α-Si:H layer, C_L and R_L denote the capacitance and resistance of the electrolyte, and C_{EDL} and R_{EDL} indicate the equivalent capacitance and resistance of the EDL between the VE and electrolyte interface.

Magnetite molecules nucleated on the illuminated surface and aggregated into NPs with the same pattern as the projected interferometric laser. Thus, the period of the patterned NPs can be controlled directly, and the grain size distribution is consistent with the

interference intensity distribution.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Grain size distribution

According to the Faraday's law of electrolysis, when a DC current flows through the electrolyte, the amount of substance $n\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ generated by the chemical reaction on an electrode (e.g. the VE/electrolyte interface) in a deposition process can be calculated by

$$n_{\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4} = \frac{Q}{zF} \quad (3)$$

$$Q = I_{ph}t \quad (4)$$

where Q is the amount of electrons received, z is the valence of Fe_3O_4 molecules and F is the Faraday constant. In Eq. (4), I_{ph} denotes the photocurrent generated in the hydrogenated amorphous silicon, and t denotes the deposition time. When the illumination and electron-hole generation are in a steady-state throughout the $\alpha\text{-Si:H}$ material, and there is only the electron contribution to the photocurrent, the photoconductivity can be written as [42]

$$\Delta\sigma_{ph} = \Phi\alpha\eta e\mu_{n0}\tau \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta\sigma_{ph}$ is the photoconductivity, Φ is the incident luminous flux per unit area, α is the absorption coefficient, η is the quantum efficiency for the electron generation, μ_{n0} is the drift mobility of the electron, and τ is the response time of photoconductivity. When the DC current is applied, the I_{ph} can be expressed as

$$I_{ph} = U\Delta\sigma_{ph}A/d \quad (6)$$

where U denotes the potential of the EDL, A is the pattern area, and d denotes the thickness of the $\alpha\text{-Si:H}$ film.

$$m_{Fe_3O_4} = V_{Fe_3O_4} \rho = A r_{Fe_3O_4} \rho = n_{Fe_3O_4} N_{Fe_3O_4} \quad (7)$$

In Eq. (7), $r_{Fe_3O_4}$ is the grain size of Fe_3O_4 NPs. $N_{Fe_3O_4}$, $m_{Fe_3O_4}$, $V_{Fe_3O_4}$ and ρ are the molar mass, mass, volume, and density of Fe_3O_4 , respectively.

Considering Eqs. (1-7), when the material of α -Si:H is not changed, $\alpha \eta e \mu_{n0} \tau N_{Fe_3O_4} / \rho z d F$ is a constant, and then the dependence of the grain size of the NPs can be expressed as

$$r_{Fe_3O_4} \propto U \Phi t \quad (8)$$

in which the grain size of the NPs is proportional to the applied potential, deposition time and laser intensity.

4.2 Laser interference irradiation-dependent grain size distribution

In this work, the intensity distribution of the two-beam interference pattern was obtained by theoretical analysis and computer simulation as shown in Fig. 1(c). The details of the simulations can be found in our previous work [30-33]. The corresponding distribution of Fe_3O_4 NPs shows that the largest NPs are mainly concentrated in the interference maxima areas and the smallest ones in the interference minimum areas. The grain sizes are distributed in a gradient way. When the incident angles and intensities of laser beams are set to the same values, the period of two-beam interference pattern is $d = \lambda / 2 \sin(\theta)$. Therefore, the period of the patterned NPs can be controlled by changing the incident wavelength λ and the incident angle θ .

It can be found from Eq. (8) that when the potential and deposition time in the LIED process are constant, the grain size distribution of the NPs is determined by interferometric laser intensity. Fig. 1(c) shows that the theoretical analysis matches well with the experimental results. The grain size distribution of NPs is also strongly dependent on the contrast of interferometric laser pattern which can be modulated by the parameters

of incident beams. When the laser intensity is lower than the conducting threshold, the hydrogenated amorphous silicon film is not conductive, and when it is beyond the saturation threshold, the contrast of the pattern is decreased. Therefore, an optimal power density of 1.5 mW cm^{-2} for the irradiated interferometric laser was chosen for each experiment.

4.3 Relationship between the grain size and applied potential

The applied potential is a key factor in the deposition of patterned Fe_3O_4 NPs, and it greatly influences the properties of EDL. As shown in Fig. 4, the influence of the potential on the deposition of NPs was investigated.

The LIEDs were carried out at constant current densities of 0.5 mA cm^{-2} , 0.8 mA cm^{-2} , 1.0 mA cm^{-2} , 1.5 mA cm^{-2} and 2.0 mA cm^{-2} , respectively. During the deposition time of 100 seconds, the potentials between the α -Si:H substrate cathode and the SCE in the electrolyte vs the deposition time were recorded, as shown in Fig. 4(a). Based on the curve, an initial charging process of the negative potential was recorded with the time of the current applied to the cathode at the beginning, due to the large capacitance of the EDL.

In the experiments, the potential is proportional to the applied current density. The SEM micrograph of bare α -Si:H substrate before deposition is shown in Fig. 4(b). Figs. 4(c-g) show the morphologies of five representative samples. With an applied potential between 0 and -1.0 V , there are not patterned NPs observed, as shown in Fig. 4(c). Figs. 4(d-f) show the micro-structures of deposited Fe_3O_4 with different potentials. The particle size increases with the decrease of the applied negative potential. This can be attributed to that the applied higher current facilitates the higher reaction efficiency of Fe_3O_4 NPs.

When the applied negative potential is lower than -3.0 V, the destruction of the hydrogenated amorphous silicon that results from the poor adherence of the film to the substrate can be observed (Fig. 4(g)). Therefore, the cathode current density for the crystallization of micro-patterned Fe₃O₄ NPs is believed to be in a narrow range between 0.8 mA cm⁻² and 1.8 mA cm⁻² for the electrodeposition. Correspondingly, the deposition potential window is between -1.6 V and -3.0 V.

4.4 Relationship between the grain size and deposition time

Figs. 5(a–e) show the SEM images of the Fe₃O₄ particles in different deposition periods, with a fixed current density of 1.0 mA cm⁻². The grain size of the deposited particles increases with the deposition time of (a) 50 s, (b) 100 s, (c) 200 s, (d) 400 s and (e) 800 s, respectively. The aggregation of Fe₃O₄ particles can be found due to the continued growth of particles and results in the formation of large Fe₃O₄ polycrystalline clusters once the α -Si:H substrate is completely covered with Fe₃O₄. Prolonging deposition duration leads to thick and dense magnetite deposits, as shown in Fig. 5(e). The average grain size of particles in the micro-pattern is linearly proportional to the deposition time, as shown in Fig. 5(f).

4.5 Grain size analysis in one T × T area

In this work, Fe₃O₄ NPs with different morphologies including tetragonal and irregular polyhedrons were synthesized. In particular, tetrahedral Fe₃O₄ NPs are featured with the regular shape, smooth surface and good crystallization [43]. Fig. 6(a) shows the SEM images of Fe₃O₄ NPs fabricated on the α -Si:H substrate by LIED method in one T × T area. The applied current density is 1.0 mA cm⁻² with the deposition time of 100 seconds.

Software Image J and software Origin were used to calculate the grain sizes of NPs. The longest axis of NPs with the good contrast between the crystallization area and the substrate in SEM images was measured using Image J, and the results were collected and plotted by Origin software, as shown in Fig. 6(b). The calculated mean size of NPs was 66.8 nm. It can be seen that the LIED method is able to fabricate patterned NPs with a near Gaussian distribution of grain sizes, giving an integrated method to control MNP morphology and localization on the surfaces with interference patterns.

Clearly, the LIED method could be improved by reducing the period of laser interference pattern to nanoscales. The minimum period of the interference pattern is the half-wavelength of incident light. Laser interference can make different patterns, e.g. dot arrays with nanoscale precision can be generated by two identical exposures. Besides fabricating micro-patterned Fe₃O₄ NPs, the LIED method is able to fabricate other MNPs or metal NPs such as copper, gold, CoPt and FePt with corresponding electrolytes.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a large area of periodically micro-patterned Fe₃O₄ NPs was fabricated by LIED method. Fe₃O₄ NPs in a periodical pattern of 5 μm line arrays were synthesized on the hydrogenated amorphous silicon photoconductive cathode during the electrodeposition controlled by two-beam laser interference irradiation. The pattern of Fe₃O₄ NPs was controlled by the interferometric laser pattern, and the nucleation and growth of Fe₃O₄ NPs were controlled by the laser interference intensity and electrochemical deposition conditions of the applied potential and deposition time. The experimental results have shown that periodical micro-patterns and grain sizes of Fe₃O₄ NPs can be fabricated in a controllable way with the LIED method. This work provides a

one-step approach in fabricating a large area of periodically micro-patterned MNPs for different potential applications.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Figure Captions

Fig. 1. (a) LIED experimental system and diagram of two-beam laser interference system. (b) Large area of Fe_3O_4 NPs fabricated on the α -Si:H surface. (c) 2D interference simulation result for two-beam laser interference pattern ($\lambda = 457 \text{ nm}$, $\theta = 2.6^\circ$) and the corresponding laser intensity curve along the line in the simulation, and the consistent distribution of Fe_3O_4 NPs with an area of $2T \times 3T$, where T is the period.

Fig. 2. (a) XPS spectra of the constituent elements for the Fe_3O_4 NPs fabricated on the α -Si:H surface with the current density of 1.0 mA cm^{-2} , deposition time of 100 seconds and irradiated interferometric laser power density of 1.5 mW cm^{-2} . (b) Detailed peaks of Fe $2p_{1/2}$ and Fe $2p_{3/2}$.

Fig. 3. (a) Mechanism of fabricating patterned Fe_3O_4 NPs by LIED. The cathode consists of the ITO glass substrate and α -Si:H film on the surface. (b) Equivalent circuit model of the LIED system, which consists of the α -Si:H film, the iron ion electrolyte and the VE/electrolyte interface.

Fig. 4. (a) Curves of potential vs time from the CP measurement under the applied current densities from (c-g): (c) 0.5 mA cm^{-2} , (d) 0.8 mA cm^{-2} , (e) 1.0 mA cm^{-2} , (f) 1.5 mA cm^{-2} and (g) 2.0 mA cm^{-2} , respectively. (b) SEM micrograph of bare α -Si:H substrate before deposition. (c-g) SEM micrographs of Fe_3O_4 NPs with an area of $2T \times 2T$.

Fig. 5. Morphologies of Fe_3O_4 particles at different deposition periods: (a) 50 s, (b) 100 s, (c) 200 s, (d) 400 s and (e) 800 s, respectively, with the current density of 1.0 mA cm^{-2} and the area of $2T \times 2T$. (f) Average grain sizes of Fe_3O_4 particles as a function of deposition time in (a-e).

Fig. 6. (a) SEM images of patterned Fe_3O_4 NPs fabricated by LIED method in an area of T

× T. (b) Counts of different grain sizes of Fe₃O₄ NPs within the area of (a).

Figures

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6